

New data about Keroplatidae (Diptera: Nematocera: Sciaroidea) in Bulgaria

Dimitar BECHEV

BECHEV D. 2006. New data about Keroplatidae (Diptera: Nematocera: Sciaroidea) in Bulgaria. – *Historia naturalis bulgarica*, 17: 93-94.

Abstract. The species *Orfelia bicolor* (Macquart), *O. bezzii* (Strobl), *Pyratula subcanariae* Chandler and *Macrocera grandis* Lundström are newly recorded for the fauna of Bulgaria. Male genitalia of *Orfelia bicolor* and *O. bezzii* are illustrated.

Key words: Diptera, Sciaroidea, Keroplatidae, Bulgaria.

Forty two species of the family Keroplatidae are known to belong to the fauna of Bulgaria (BECHEV, 2002). In the present work four species are newly recorded for the fauna of Bulgaria and new distributional data about *Macrocera gemagea* Bechev are given.

Keroplatinae

Orfelia bicolor (Macquart, 1826)

Northern Black Sea Coast: Kamchia Reserve, UTM: NH76, 10 m a. s. l., 8.06.1990, 1♂ and 4.07.1985, 1♂.

New to Bulgaria. The male genitalia (Fig. 1) resembles *O. bicolor* in ventral view (CHANDLER, 2001: Fig. 6), but the scutum is yellow, with three brown longitudinal stripes as *O. basalis* (Winnertz, 1863). The scutum of *bicolor* is entirely dark. On the basis of these differences one can make a guess that *basalis* is probably a good species but not a synonym of *bicolor* as is considered recently. *O. bicolor* is widely distributed in Europe.

Orfelia bezzii (Strobl, 1909)

Western Stara Planina Mts: Byalata Voda Hut, UTM: FN88, 775 m a. s. l., 26.06.1982, 1♂; Vratsa, UTM: GN08, 350 m a.s.l., 26.06.1988, 2♂♂; Middle Stara Planina Mts: Zlatishki Prohod Pass, UTM: KH64, 1000 m a.s.l., 18.07.1983, 1♂; Belasitsa Mt.: Belasitsa Hut, UTM: FL87, 720 m a.s.l., 23.06.1992, 1♂.

Figs 1-3. Male genitalia: 1 – *Orfelia bicolor*, ventral view; 2 – *O. bezzii*, ventral view; 3 – the same, apex of the gonostyle.

New to Bulgaria. Known from Belgium and Hungary only. Male genitalia – Figs 2 and 3.

Pyratula subcanariae Chandler, 2001

Eastern Danubian Plain: near Orlova Chuka Cave, UTM: MJ12, 150 m a.s.l., 13.05.1996, 2 ♂♂.
New to Bulgaria. Known from Switzerland only.

Macrocerinae

Macrocera gemagea Bechev, 1991

Northern Black Sea Coast: Shkorpilovtsi, UTM: NH76, 10 m a.s.l., 8.06.1990, 1♂, 1♀; south of Varna, UTM: NH76, 20 m a.s.l., 9.06.1990, 1♂, 1♀.

Up to now known from the type locality (West Predbalkan: Veslets) only.

Macrocera grandis Lundström, 1912

Rila Mt.: Rila Monastery, UTM: FM96, 1150 m a.s.l., 27.08.1989, 1 ♀.

New to Bulgaria. Known from Northwestern Russia, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Latvia and Germany. Identification is made on the basis of a single female only.

References

- BECHEV D. 2002. Check list of the fungus gnats of the families Bolitophilidae, Diadocidiidae, Ditomyiidae, Keroplatidae and Mycetophilidae in Bulgaria (Diptera: Nematocera). – Trav. Sci. Univ. Plovdiv, Biologie, Animalia, 38, 6: 81-112.
- CHANDLER P. 2001. Fungus gnats (Diptera: Sciaroidea) new to Britain. – Br. J. Ent. Nat. Hist., 13: 215-243.

Received: 11.07.2005

Author's address:
Dr. Dimitar Bechev
University of Plovdiv
Tzar Assen Str. 24
BG-4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria
E-mail: bechev@pu.acad.bg

Нови данни за Keroplatidae (Diptera: Nematocera: Sciaroidea) в България

Димитър БЕЧЕВ

(Р е з ю м е)

Давам се нови данни за разпространението *Macrocera gemagea* Bechev и се съобщавам *Orfelia bicolor* (Macquart), *O. bezzii* (Strobl), *Pyratula subcanariae* Chandler и *Macrocera grandis* Lundström като нови за фауната на България.